

Vague Join Semi L-Filter of Lattice Homomorphism

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Abstract:-

In this paper contains vague join semi L-filter, unit vague value, zero vague value on vague join semi L-filter with suitable examples. And define the homomorphism of vague join semi-lattice also some of their properties have been investigated.

Keywords: - Vague join semi L-filter, vague join semi L- filter lattice, Vague join semi L-filter of lattice homomorphism.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of Lattice was first defined by Dedekind in 1897 and then developed by Birkhoff, G., imposed an operation an open problem "Is there a common abstraction which includes Boolean algebra, Boolean rings and lattice ordered group or L-group is an algebraic structure connecting lattice and group. To answer this problem many common abstractions, namely dually residuated lattice ordered semigroups, commutative lattice ordered groups, lattice ordered rings, lattice ordered near rings and lattice ordered semirings are presented. Among them the algebraic structure lattice ordered semirings or L-semiring was introduced by Ranga Rao, P., [13]. Also the concept proposed by Zadeh, L. A. [16] defining a fuzzy subset A of a given universe X characterizing the membership of an element x of X belonging to A by means of a membership function $\mu_A(x)$ defined from X into $[0, 1]$ has revolutionized the theory of Mathematical modeling. Decision making etc., in handling the imprecise real life situations mathematically. Now several branches of fuzzy mathematics like fuzzy algebra, fuzzy topology, fuzzy control theory, fuzzy measure theory etc., have emerged. But in the decision making, the fuzzy theory takes care of membership of an element x only, that is the evidence against x belonging to A . It is felt by several decision makers and researchers that in proper decision making, the evidence belongs to A and evidence not belongs to A are both necessary and how much X belongs to A or how much x does not belongs to A are necessary.

Several generalizations of Zadeh's fuzzy set theory have been proposed, such as L-fuzzy sets [4]. Interval valued fuzzy sets, Intuitionistic fuzzy sets by Atanassov, K. T. [1], Vague sets [3] are mathematically equivalent. Any such set A of a given Universe X can be characterized by means of a pair of function (t_A, f_A) where $t_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $f_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $0 \leq t_A(x) + f_A(x) \leq 1$ for all x in X . The set $t_A(x)$ is called the truth function or membership function and the set $f_A(x)$ is called false function or non membership function and $t_A(x)$ gives the evidence of how much x belongs to A , $f_A(x)$ gives the evidence of how much x does not belongs to A . These concepts are being applied in several areas like decision-making, fuzzy control, knowledge discovery and fault diagnosis etc. It is believed the vague sets (or equivalently intuitionistic fuzzy sets) will more useful in decision making, and other areas of Mathematical modeling. Through Atanassov's intuitionistic fuzzy sets, Gau and Buehrer, D. J. and some other areas of Mathematical modeling. Since then the theory of fuzzy sets developed extensively and embraced almost all subjects like engineering science and technology. But the membership function $\mu_A(x)$ gives only a approximation belong to A . To avoid this and obtain a better estimation and analysis of data decision making. Gau, W. L. and Bueher, D. J. [3] have initiated the study of vague sets with the hope that they form a better tool to understand, interpret and solve real life problems which are in general vague, than the theory of vague sets do. Ranjit Biswas [9] initiated the study of vague groups by Ramakrishna, N. [6], [7], [8] and Eswarlal, T. [2] are grate extended the study of vague algebra. The objective of this paper is to contribute further to the study of vague algebra by introducing the concepts of vague join semi lattice, vague join semi L-filter, vague cut-set, unit vague set and zero vague set etc on vague join semi lattice with suitable examples.

2. Preliminaries

In this section we briefly present the necessary material on frequently lattices, complete lattices and illustrate with examples.

Definition 1.1 [4]

A poset (L, \leq) is called a lattice if $\sup\{x, y\}$ also denoted by $(x \vee y)$ and $\inf\{x, y\}$ also denoted by $(x \wedge y)$ exists for every pair of elements x, y in L .

Definition 1.2 A lattice (L, \leq) in which every subset of L has g.l.b and l.u.b in it is called a complete lattice.

Definition 1.3[4] A lattice L is said to be distributive if it satisfies the $x \wedge (y \vee z) = (x \wedge y) \vee (x \wedge z)$ and $x \vee (y \wedge z) = (x \vee y) \wedge (x \vee z)$ for all x, y in L .

Definition 1.4[4] A lattice L is said to be bounded if L has least element and greatest element. Usually least element of L is denoted by 0_L and greatest element is denoted by 1_L .

Definition 1.5[4] A join semi lattice or semilattice is a non-empty set S with binary operation \vee defined on it satisfies the following.

1. Idempotent: $(a \vee a) = a$
2. Commutative law : $a \vee b = b \vee a$
3. Associative law: $a \vee (b \vee c) = (a \vee b) \vee c$ for all $a, b, c \in S$
4. Any two elements in S have a least upper bound.

Definition 1.6[4] A semi lattice is a non-empty set S with binary relation \leq defined on it it satisfies the following conditions.

1. \leq is reflexive : $a \leq a$ for all $a \in S$
2. \leq is anti symmetric : $a \leq b$ and $b \leq a$ implies $a = b$
3. \leq is transitive law: $a \leq b, b \leq c$ implies $a \leq c$, for all $a, b, c \in S$.

Definition 1.7 Let A be a join semi lattice A fuzzy set $\mu_A: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ called fuzzy join semi lattice of A if it satisfies the property $\mu_A(x \vee y) \geq \min \{ \mu_A(x), \mu_A(y) \}$ for all x, y in X .

Example 1.8. Let $A = \{ 0, x_1, x_2, x_3, 1 \}$ be a semi lattice. Then it's a fuzzy join semi lattice of μ_A of A given by $\mu_A = \{ (0, 0.8), (x_1, 0.7), (x_2, 0.5), (x_3, 0.6) \}$.

Definition 1.9 [10] Let $A = (t_A, f_A)$ and $B = (t_B, f_B)$ be two vague sets of sets X then their intersection is defined as $(A \cap B) = (t_A \cap t_B, f_A \cap f_B)$

where $(t_A \cap t_B) = \min \{ t_A^{(x)}, t_B^{(y)} \}$ and $(f_A \cap f_B) = \max \{ f_A^{(x)}, f_B^{(y)} \}$.

Definition 1.10 [10] Let $A = (t_A, f_A)$ be a set of X its complement is defined as $A^1 = (t_A^1, f_A^1)$

Where $t_A^1 = 1 - f_A$ and $f_A^1 = 1 - t_A$.

Definition 1.11 [10] The vague set A of a set X with $t_A(x) = 0$ and $f_A(x) = 1$, for $x \in X$, for all $x \in X$ is called the zero vague set of X . It is denoted by $\bar{0} = (0, 1)$.

Definition 1.10 [10] The vague set A of a set X with $t_A(x) = 1$ and $f_A(x) = 0$, for $x \in X$, for all $x \in X$ is called the unit vague set of X . It is denoted by $\bar{1} = (1, 0)$.

Definition 1.12 A vague sets $A = (t_A, f_A), B = (t_B, f_B)$ where $t_A: X \rightarrow [0, 1], f_A: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$
 $0 \leq t_A(x) + f_A(x) \leq 1$

Definition 1.14 Two Vague sets A and B are equal, written as $A = B$ if and only if $A \subseteq B$ and $B \subseteq A$ i.e. $t_A = t_B$ and $f_A = f_B$.

Definition 1.15[10]: A vague set A is said to be contained in the vague set B, i.e. $A \subseteq B$ iff $t_A \leq t_B$ and $f_A \geq f_B$.

Definition 1.16: Vague sets A and B are equal, written as $A = B$, iff $A \subseteq B$ and $B \subseteq A$. i.e., $t_A = t_B, f_A = f_B$.

Definition 1.17: Let $A = (t_A, f_A), B = (t_B, f_B)$ be two vague sets of a set X then their union is defined as $A \cup B = (t_{A \cup B}, f_{A \cup B})$ where, $t_{A \cup B} = \max\{t_A, t_B\}$ and $f_{A \cup B} = \min\{f_A, f_B\}$.

Definition 1.18: Let $A = (t_A, f_A), B = (t_B, f_B)$ be two vague sets of set X then their intersection is defined as $A \cap B = (t_{A \cap B}, f_{A \cap B})$

where, $t_{A \cap B} = \min\{t_A, t_B\}$ and $f_{A \cap B} = \max\{f_A, f_B\}$.

Definition 1.19 [10] The interval $[t_A^{(x)}, 1-f_A^{(x)}]$ is called the vague value of $x \in A$, and it is denoted by $V_A^{(x)} = [t_A^{(x)}, 1-f_A^{(x)}]$.

1. $t_A(x+y) \geq \wedge \{t_A(x), t_A(y)\}$
2. $t_A(xy) \geq \wedge \{t_A(x), t_A(y)\}$
3. $t_A(x \vee y) \geq \wedge \{t_A(x), t_A(y)\}$
4. $t_A(x \wedge y) \geq \wedge \{t_A(x), t_A(y)\}$.

3. VAGUE JOIN SEMI L-FILTER :

In this section We now introduce the concepts of vague join semi L-filter, vague join semi ideal, unit vague value, zero vague value on vague join semi L-filter with suitable examples.

Definition 3.1.: $A=(t_A, f_A)$ be a vague semi lattice of a semi lattice X is said to be vague join semi L-ideal If it satisfies the following conditions.

1. $t_A(x \vee y) \geq \min \{t_A(x), t_A(y)\}$ and
2. $f_A(x \vee y) \leq \max \{f_A(x), f_A(y)\}$, for all x in X.

Definition 3.2: $A=(t_A, f_A)$ be a vague semi lattice of a semi lattice X is said to be vague join semi L-filter If it satisfies the following conditions.

1. $t_A(x \vee y) \leq \max \{t_A(x), t_A(y)\}$ and
2. $f_A(x \vee y) \geq \min \{f_A(x), f_A(y)\}$, for all x in X.

Example 3.3: Let $X=\{0,a,b,c,1\}$ be a join semi lattice $A=(t_A, f_A)$ be a vague join semi lattice of a join semi lattice X then A is vague join semi L-filter.

Sol:- Let $X=\{0,a,b,c,1\}$ be a join semi lattice

$A = \{ (0,0.6,0.4), (a,0.5,0.5), (b,0.4,0.6), (c,0.3,0.7), (1,0.2,0.8) \}$ be a s vague join semi lattice of a semi lattice X.

(a) (i) $t_A(0 \vee a) = t_A(0) = 0.6$ and $\max \{ t_A(0), t_A(a) \} = \max \{ 0.6, 0.5 \} = 0.6$
 implies $t_A(0 \vee a) \leq \max \{ t_A(0), t_A(a) \}$

(ii) $t_A(a \vee b) = t_A(a) = 0.5$ and $\max \{ t_A(a), t_A(b) \} = \max \{ 0.5, 0.4 \} = 0.5$
 implies $t_A(a \vee b) \leq \max \{ t_A(a), t_A(b) \}$.

(iii) $t_A(b \vee c) = t_A(b) = 0.4$ and $\max \{ t_A(b), t_A(c) \} = \max \{ 0.4, 0.3 \} = 0.4$
 implies $t_A(b \vee c) \leq \max \{ t_A(b), t_A(c) \}$.

(iv) $t_A(c \vee 1) = t_A(c) = 0.3$ and $\max \{ t_A(c), t_A(1) \} = \max \{ 0.3, 0.2 \} = 0.3$
 implies $t_A(c \vee 1) \leq \max \{ t_A(c), t_A(1) \} = 0.3$

(b) (i) $f_A(0 \vee a) = f_A(a) = 0.5$ and $\max \{ f_A(0), f_A(a) \} = \min \{ 0.4, 0.5 \} = 0.4$
 implies $f_A(0 \vee a) \geq \min \{ f_A(0), f_A(a) \}$.

(ii) $f_A(a \vee b) = f_A(b) = 0.5$ and $\max \{ f_A(a), f_A(b) \} = \min \{ 0.5, 0.6 \} = 0.5$
 implies $f_A(a \vee b) \geq \min \{ f_A(a), f_A(b) \}$.

(iii) $f_A(b \vee c) = f_A(c) = 0.7$ and $\min \{ f_A(b), f_A(c) \} = \min \{ 0.6, 0.7 \} = 0.6$
 implies $f_A(b \vee c) \geq \min \{ f_A(b), f_A(c) \}$.

(iv) $f_A(c \vee 1) = f_A(1) = 0.8$ and $\min \{ f_A(c), f_A(1) \} = \min \{ 0.7, 0.8 \} = 0.7$
 Implies $f_A(c \vee 1) \geq \min \{ f_A(c), f_A(1) \}$.

(v) $f_A(1 \vee 0) = f_A(1) = 0.8$ and $\min \{ f_A(1), f_A(0) \} = \min \{ 0.8, 0.4 \} = 0.4$
 Implies $f_A(1 \vee 0) \geq \min \{ f_A(1), f_A(0) \}$.

Therefore $A = \{ (0,0.6,0.4), (a,0.5,0.5), (b,0.4,0.6), (c,0.3,0.7), (1,0.2,0.8) \}$ be a vague join semi L-filter.

Example 3.4 : Let $X=\{0,a,b,c,1\}$ be a join semi lattice $A=(t_A, f_A)$ be a vague join semi lattice of a join semi lattice X then A is vague join semi L-filter

Sol:- Let $X=\{0,a,b,c,1\}$ be a semi lattice

$A=\{(0,0.6,0.4),(a,0.5,0.4),(b,0.6,0.4),(c,0.2,0.7),(1,0.3,0.8)\}$ be a s vague join semi lattice of a semi lattice X .

(a) (i) $t_A(0 \vee a) = t_A(0) = 0.6$ and $\max \{ t_A(0), t_A(a) \} = \max \{ 0.6, 0.5 \} = 0.6$

implies $t_A(0 \vee a) \leq \max \{ t_A(0), t_A(a) \}$

(ii) $t_A(a \vee b) = t_A(b) = 0.6$ and $\max \{ t_A(a), t_A(b) \} = \max \{ 0.5, 0.6 \} = 0.6$

implies $t_A(a \vee b) \leq \max \{ t_A(a), t_A(b) \}$.

(iii) $t_A(b \vee c) = t_A(b) = 0.6$ and $\max \{ t_A(b), t_A(c) \} = \max \{ 0.6, 0.3 \} = 0.6$

implies $t_A(b \vee c) \leq \max \{ t_A(b), t_A(c) \}$.

(iv) $t_A(c \vee 1) = t_A(1) = 0.3$ and $\max \{ t_A(c), t_A(1) \} = \max \{ 0.2, 0.3 \} = 0.3$

implies $t_A(c \vee 1) \leq \max \{ t_A(c), t_A(1) \} = 0.3$

(b) (i) $f_A(0 \vee a) = f_A(a) = 0.4$ and $\max \{ f_A(0), f_A(a) \} = \min \{ 0.4, 0.4 \} = 0.4$

implies $f_A(0 \vee a) \geq \min \{ f_A(0), f_A(a) \}$.

(ii) $f_A(a \vee b) = f_A(b) = 0.4$ and $\max \{ f_A(a), f_A(b) \} = \min \{ 0.4, 0.4 \} = 0.4$

implies $f_A(a \vee b) \geq \min \{ f_A(a), f_A(b) \}$.

(iii) $f_A(b \vee c) = f_A(c) = 0.7$ and $\min \{ f_A(b), f_A(c) \} = \min \{ 0.4, 0.7 \} = 0.4$

implies $f_A(b \vee c) \geq \min \{ f_A(b), f_A(c) \}$.

(iv) $f_A(c \vee 1) = f_A(1) = 0.8$ and $\min \{ f_A(c), f_A(1) \} = \min \{ 0.7, 0.8 \} = 0.7$

Implies $f_A(c \vee 1) \geq \min \{ f_A(c), f_A(1) \}$.

(v) $f_A(1 \vee 0) = f_A(1) = 0.8$ and $\min \{ f_A(1), f_A(0) \} = \min \{ 0.8, 0.4 \} = 0.4$

0.8 and $\min \{ f_A(1), f_A(0) \} = 0.4$

Implies $f_A(1 \vee 0) \geq \min \{ f_A(1), f_A(0) \}$.

$f_A(1 \vee 0) \geq \min \{ f_A(1), f_A(0) \}$

Therefore $A = \{ (0,0.6,0.4), (a,0.5,0.4), (b,0.6,0.4), (c,0.2,0.7), (1,0.3,0.8) \}$ be a vague join semi L-filter.

Theorem 3.5 Let $A = (t_A, f_A)$, $B = (t_B, f_B)$ and $C = (t_C, f_C)$ be any three vague join semi L-filters of a vague semi lattice X. Then the following are true.

- (i) $A \subseteq B$ iff $t_A(x) \leq t_B(x)$ and $f_A(x) \leq f_B(x)$ for all x in X
- (ii) $A = B$ iff $t_A(x) = t_B(x)$ and $f_A(x) = f_B(x)$ for all x in X
- (iii) $\bar{A} = \{ (x, f_A(x), t_A(x)) / x \in X \}$
- (iv) $A \cap B = \{ (x, \min\{t_A(x), t_B(x)\}, \max\{f_A(x), f_B(x)\}) / x \in X \}$
- (v) $A \cup B = \{ (x, \max\{t_A(x), t_B(x)\}, \min\{f_A(x), f_B(x)\}) / x \in X \}$
- (vi) $[A] = \{ (x, t_A(x), 1 - t_A(x)) / x \in X \}$
- (vii) $\langle A \rangle = \{ (x, f_A(x), f(x)) / x \in X \}$.

Theorem 3.6 Intersection of any two vague join semi L-filters is also vague join semi L-filter of a vague semi lattice.

Proof: Let A be vague join semi lattice

$A = (t_A, f_A)$ and $B = (t_B, f_B)$ are two vague join semi L-filters of a vague join semilattice A.

To prove that $(A \cap B)$ is a vague join semi L-filter of vague semilattice.

i.e $(t_A(x) \cap t_B(x), f_A(x) \cap f_B(x))$ is a vague join semi L-filter of A.

let $x, y \in (t_A \cap t_B)$ implies $x, y \in t_A$ and $x, y \in t_B$

implies $(x \vee y) \in t_A$ and $(x \vee y) \in t_B$

implies $(x \vee y) \in (t_A \cap t_B)$.

$(t_A \cap t_B)$ is also vague join semi L-filter of A.....(3.7.1)

let $x, y \in (f_A \cap f_B)$ implies $x, y \in f_A$ and $x, y \in f_B$

implies $(x \vee y) \in f_A$ and $(x \vee y) \in f_B$

implies $(x \vee y) \in (f_A \cap f_B)$.

$(f_A \cap f_B)$ is also vague join semi L-filter of A.....(3.7.2).

Therefore from (3.7.1) and (3.7.2) $(A \cap B)$ is a vague join semi L-filter of A.

Theorem 3.7 The complement of an vague join semi L-filter is an vague join semi L-ideal.

Proof: Let $A = (t_A, f_A)$ be a vague join semi L-filter.

i.e 1. $t_A(x \vee y) \leq \max\{t_A(x), t_A(y)\}$ and 2. $f_A(x \vee y) \geq \min\{f_A(x), f_A(y)\}$, for all x in X.

To prove that complement of A is an vague join semi L-ideal

i.e 1. $t_A(x \vee y) \geq \min \{ t_A(x), t_A(y) \}$ and 2. $f_A(x \vee y) \leq \max \{ f_A(x), f_A(y) \}$, for all x in X .

Now the complement of A is defined by $\bar{A} = (x, f_{\bar{A}}(x), t_{\bar{A}}(x))$ where $t_{\bar{A}} = f_A(x)$ and $f_{\bar{A}} = t_A$

here $t_{\bar{A}}^{(x)} = f_A(x)$ and $f_{\bar{A}}^{(x)} = t_A(x)$

For (i) $t_{\bar{A}}^{(x \vee y)} = f_A(x \vee y) \geq \min \{ f_A(x), f_A(y) \} \geq \min \{ t_{\bar{A}}^{(x)}, t_{\bar{A}}^{(y)} \}$

Implies $t_{\bar{A}}^{(x \vee y)} \geq \min \{ f_{\bar{A}}^{(x)}, f_{\bar{A}}^{(y)} \}$

For (ii) $f_{\bar{A}}^{(x \vee y)} = t_A(x \vee y) \leq \max \{ t_A(x), t_A(y) \} \leq \max \{ f_{\bar{A}}^{(x)}, f_{\bar{A}}^{(y)} \}$

Implies $f_{\bar{A}}^{(x \vee y)} \leq \max \{ f_{\bar{A}}^{(x)}, f_{\bar{A}}^{(y)} \}$.

Therefore the complement of A is a vague join semi L-ideal.

Theorem 3.8 If $A = (t_A, f_A)$ be a vague join semi L-filter. Then $[A] = (t_A, 1 - t_A)$ is a vague join semi L-filter of A .

Proof:- Let A be a vague join semi L-filter. Let $D = [A]$ then $t_D = t_A, f_D = 1 - f_A$

To prove that D is a vague join semi L-filter.

(i) $t_D(x \vee y) = t_A(x \vee y) \leq \max \{ t_A(x), t_A(y) \} \leq \max \{ t_D(x), t_D(y) \}$.

Therefore $t_D(x \vee y) \leq \max \{ t_D(x), t_D(y) \}$

(ii) $f_D(x \vee y) = 1 - t_A(x \vee y) \geq 1 - \max \{ f_A(x), f_A(y) \} = \min \{ 1 - t_A(x), 1 - t_A(y) \} = \min \{ f_D(x), f_D(y) \}$

Therefore $f_D(x \vee y) \geq \min \{ f_D(x), f_D(y) \}$

Hence D is a vague join semi L-filter.

Theorem 3.9 If $A = (t_A, f_A)$ be a vague join semi L-filter. Then $[A] = (1 - f_A, t_A)$ is also a vague join semi L-filter of A .

Proof: Let A be a vague join semi L-filter.

i.e 1. $t_A(x \vee y) \leq \max \{ t_A(x), t_A(y) \}$ and 2. $f_A(x \vee y) \geq \min \{ f_A(x), f_A(y) \}$, for all x in X .

To prove that $[A] = (1 - f_A, t_A)$ is a vague join semi L-filter.

Let $D = [A] = (1 - f_A, t_A)$ implies $t_D = 1 - f_A, f_D = t_A$

(i) $t_D(x \vee y) = 1 - f_A(x \vee y) \leq 1 - \min \{ f_A(x), f_A(y) \} = \max \{ 1 - f_A(x), 1 - f_A(y) \} = \max \{ t_D(x), t_D(y) \}$

Therefore $t_D(x \vee y) \leq \max \{ t_D(x), t_D(y) \}$

(ii) $f_D(x \vee y) = t_A(x \vee y) \geq \min \{ t_A(x), t_A(y) \} = \min \{ f_D(x), f_D(y) \}$

$f_D(xVy) \geq \min\{f_D(x), f_D(y)\}$.
 D is a vague join semi L-filter.

Theorem 3.10 If $A=(t_A, f_A)$ be a vague join semi L-filter X. Then $t_A, 1-f_A$ are vague join semi L-filter.

Proof: Let $A=(t_A, f_A)$ be a vague join semi L-filter X.

- (i) Let $D=(t_A, f_A)$ be a vague set of X then $t_D = t_A$
 $t_D(xVy) = t_A(xVy) \leq \max\{t_A(x), t_A(y)\} = \{t_D(x), t_D(y)\}$
 Therefore $t_D(xVy) \leq \{t_D(x), t_D(y)\}$.
- (ii) Let $C=1-f_A$
 $t_C(xVy) = 1-f_A(xVy) \leq 1-\min\{f_A(x), f_A(y)\} = \max\{1-f_A(x), 1-f_A(y)\}$
 $t_C(xVy) = \max\{f_C(x), f_C(y)\}$
 $1-f_A$ is vague join semi L-filter.

4.Vague join semi L-filter of Lattice Homomorphism :

Definition 4.1 Let $A=(t_A, f_A)$ be an vague join semi L-filter of a join semi lattice X, Then the true α -cut set on vague join semi L-filter can be defined by $t_A\alpha = \{x \in X : t_A(x) \leq \alpha\}$, for all $\alpha \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 4.2 Let $A=(t_A, f_A)$ vague join semi L-filter of a join semi lattice X, Then the false α -cut on vague join semi L-filter can be defined by

$f_A\alpha = \{x \in S : f_A(x) \geq \alpha\}$, for all $\alpha \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 4.3 $A=(t_A, f_A)$ vague join semi L-filter of a join semi lattice X, Then vague cut-set on vague join semi L-filter can be defined by

$A_{(\alpha, \beta)}(x) = \{x \in X : t_A(x) \leq \alpha \text{ and } f_A(x) \geq \beta\}$, for all $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]$.

Example: 4.4: $A=\{(0,0.7,0.3),(a,0.6,0.4),(b,0.5,0.4),(c,0.6,0.4),(1,0.5,0.2)\}$ be a vague join semi L-filter and $\alpha=0.5$ and $\beta=0.4 \in [0,1]$. Then the Vague cut-set on vague join semi L-filter is $A_{(\alpha, \beta)}(x) = \{(a,0.5,0.4),(c,0.2,0.7)\}$.

Theorem 4.5 If $A=(t_A, f_A)$ be a vague join semi L-filter of join semi lattice X. Then vague-cut $A_{(\alpha, \beta)}(x) = \{x \in X : t_A(x) \leq \alpha \text{ and } f_A(x) \geq \beta\}$, for all $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]$ is a vague join semi L-filter of A.

Proof: Let $x, y \in A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$ then $t_A^{(x)} \leq \alpha$ and $f_A^{(x)} \geq \beta$

Implies $t_A^{(x \vee y)} \leq \max\{t_A^{(x)}, t_A^{(y)}\} \leq \alpha$.

Therefore $(x \vee y) \in A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$

Let $x, y \in A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$ then $f_A^{(x)} \geq \beta$, $f_A^{(y)} \geq \beta$

Implies $f_A^{(x \vee y)} \geq \min\{f_A^{(x)}, f_A^{(y)}\} \geq \beta$

Therefore $f_A^{(x \vee y)} \in A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$

Hence $A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$ is a vague join semi L-filter of A.

Theorem 4.6 If $A=(t_A, f_A)$ be a vague join semi L-filter of a join semi lattice X if and only if and only if vague-cut $A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)} = \{x \in X : t_A^{(x)} \leq \alpha \text{ and } f_A^{(x)} \geq \beta\}$, for all $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]$ is a vague join semi L-filter of A.

Proof: Assume that $A=(t_A, f_A)$ be a vague join semi L-filter of a semi lattice X then vague-cut $A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)} = \{x \in X : t_A^{(x)} \leq \alpha \text{ and } f_A^{(x)} \geq \beta\}$, for all $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]$ is a vague join semi L-filter of A. (since proof of theorem 3.10).

Conversely suppose that vague-cut $A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$ is a vague join semi L-filter of A.

Let $x, y \in A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$ implies $t_A^{(x)} \leq \alpha$ and $f_A^{(x)} \geq \beta$

Implies $\max\{t_A^{(x)}, t_A^{(y)}\} \leq \alpha$ implies $t_A^{(x \vee y)} \leq \alpha$ implies $(x \vee y) \in A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$

Therefore $t_A^{(x \vee y)} \leq \max\{t_A^{(x)}, t_A^{(y)}\}$.

And Let $x, y \in A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$ implies $f_A^{(x)} \geq \beta$ and $f_A^{(y)} \geq \beta$

Implies $\min\{f_A^{(x)}, f_A^{(y)}\} \geq \beta$ implies $f_A^{(x \vee y)} \geq \beta$ implies $(x \vee y) \in A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$

Therefore $f_A^{(x \vee y)} \geq \min\{f_A^{(x)}, f_A^{(y)}\}$.

Hence A is a vague join semi L-filter.

Theorem 4.7 The intersection of two vague-cut sets of a vague join semi L-filters of a join semi L-filter A is also vague cut-set of a vague join semi L-filter of A.

Proof: Let $A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)} = \{ x \in X : t_A^{(x)} \leq \alpha \text{ and } f_A^{(x)} \geq \beta \}$, for all $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]$

$B_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)} = \{ x \in X : t_B^{(x)} \leq \alpha \text{ and } f_B^{(x)} \geq \beta \}$, for all $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]$ are two vague cut-sets of a vague join semi L-filter of A, B respectively.

(i) Let $x, y \in A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$ and Let $x, y \in B_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$

Implies $t_A^{(x)} \leq \alpha, t_A^{(y)} \leq \alpha$ and $t_B^{(x)} \leq \alpha, t_B^{(y)} \leq \alpha$

Implies $(x \vee y) \in A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$ and $(x \vee y) \in B_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$

Implies $(x \vee y) \in (A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)} \cap B_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}) \dots\dots\dots(4.7.1).$

(ii) Let $x, y \in A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$ and Let $x, y \in B_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$

Implies $f_A^{(x)} \geq \beta, f_A^{(y)} \geq \beta$ and $f_B^{(x)} \geq \beta, f_B^{(y)} \geq \beta$

Implies $(x \vee y) \in A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$ and $(x \vee y) \in B_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}$

Implies $(x \vee y) \in (A_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)} \cap B_{(\alpha, \beta)}^{(x)}) \dots\dots\dots(4.7.2).$

From(4.7.1) and (4.7.2) The intersection of two vague –cut sets of a vague join semi L-filters of a join semi L-filter A is also vague cut-set of a vague join semi L-filter of A.

Hence the theorem proved.

4.Vague Join Semi L-Filter of Lattice Homomorphism:

Definition: 4.8 Let L_1 and L_2 be a lattices, a mapping $g: L_1 \rightarrow L_2$ is called homomorphism if

$$1.g(a \vee b) = g(a) \vee g(b) \quad 2.g(a \wedge b) = g(a) \wedge g(b) \text{ for all } a, b \in L.$$

Definition: 4.9 Let L_1 and L_2 be a lattices ,a mapping $g: L_1 \rightarrow L_2$ is called isomorphism if

If g is one- one onto homomorphism

Definition: 4.10 Let L_1 and L_2 be a lattices ,a mapping $g: L_1 \rightarrow L_2$ is called endomorphism if

If g is onto homomorphism.

Definition 4.11 Let L_1 and L_2 be two Lattices and $\varphi: L_1 \rightarrow L_2$ be a mapping. Let A be L vague set of L_1 . Then the image of a L-vague set A can be defined by

$$V_{\varphi(A)}(x) = (t_{\varphi(A)}(x), f_{\varphi(A)}(x)) \text{ where } t_{\varphi(A)}(x) = t_A(\varphi(x)) \text{ and } f_{\varphi(A)}(x) = f_A(\varphi(x)).$$

Definition 4.12 Let L_1 and L_2 are two vague join semi-lattices and $\varphi: L_1 \rightarrow L_2$ be a mapping. Let A be a L vague set of L_1 . Then the inverse image of a vague join semi-lattice of a vague set A can be defined by

$$V_{\varphi^{-1}(A)}(x) = (t_{\varphi^{-1}(A)}(x), f_{\varphi^{-1}(A)}(x))$$

where $t_{\varphi^{-1}(A)}(x) = t_A \varphi^{-1}(x)$ and $f_{\varphi^{-1}(A)}(x) = f_A \varphi^{-1}(x)$.

Theorem 4.13 Let L_1 and L_2 be any two vague join semi-lattices and $\varphi: L_1 \rightarrow L_2$ be a join semi-lattice homomorphism. Then the homographic image of vague join semi-lattices of L_1 is a join semi- L -vague lattice L_2 .

Proof: Let L_1 and L_2 be any two vague join semi- lattices and

$\varphi: L_1 \rightarrow L_2$ be a homomorphism. Let $x, y \in S_1$.

(i) Let $x, y \in S_1$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{We have } t_A(\varphi(x) \vee \varphi(y)) &= t_A(\varphi(x \vee y)) \\ &\geq \min\{t_A(xy)\} \\ &\geq \min\{t_A(x), t_A(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

(Since φ is a homomorphism.)

$$\geq \min\{t_A(\varphi(x)), t_A(\varphi(y))\}$$

Therefore $f_A(\varphi(x) \varphi(y)) \geq \min\{t_A(\varphi(x)), t_A(\varphi(y))\}$

Therefore $t_A(\varphi(x) \vee \varphi(y)) \geq \min\{t_A(\varphi(x)), t_A(\varphi(y))\}$

(ii) Let $x, y \in S_1$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{We have } f_A(\varphi(x) \vee \varphi(y)) &= f_A(\varphi(x \vee y)) \\ &\leq \max\{f_A(x \vee y)\} \\ &\leq \max\{f_A(x), f_A(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

(Since φ is a homomorphism.)

$$\leq \max\{f_A(\varphi(x)), f_A(\varphi(y))\}$$

$$\text{Therefore } f_A(\varphi(x) \vee \varphi(y)) \leq \max\{f_A(\varphi(x)), f_A(\varphi(y))\}$$

We have the homomorphic image of L-vague semi-rings of L_1 is a L-vague lattice L_2 .

Hence the theorem follows.

Theorem 4.14 Let $\varphi: L_1 \rightarrow L_2$ be a vague join semi-lattice homomorphism from L_1 into L_2 . Let B be a vague join semi-lattice of L_2 . Then $\varphi^{-1}(B)$ is vague join semi-lattice L_1 .

Proof: - Let B be a vague join semi-lattice of L_2 and let $\varphi: L_1 \rightarrow L_2$ be a vague join semi-lattice homomorphism from L_1 into L_2 for all

(a) Let $x, y \in L_1$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{We have } t_A(\varphi^{-1}(x) \vee \varphi^{-1}(y)) &= t_A(\varphi^{-1}(x \vee y)) \\ &\geq \min\{t_A(x \vee y)\} \\ &\geq \min\{t_A(x), t_A(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

(Since φ is a homomorphism.)

$$\geq \min\{t_A(\varphi^{-1}(x)), t_A(\varphi^{-1}(y))\}$$

$$\text{Therefore } t_A(\varphi^{-1}(x) \vee \varphi^{-1}(y)) \leq \min\{t_A(\varphi^{-1}(x)), t_A(\varphi^{-1}(y))\}$$

(b) Let $x, y \in L_1$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{We have } f_A(\varphi^{-1}(x) \vee \varphi^{-1}(y)) &= f_A(\varphi^{-1}(x \vee y)) \\ &\leq \max \{ f_A(x \vee y) \} \\ &\leq \max \{ f_A(x), f_A(y) \} \end{aligned}$$

(Since φ is a homomorphism.)

$$\leq \max \{ f_A(\varphi^{-1}(x)), f_A(\varphi^{-1}(y)) \}$$

Therefore $f_A(\varphi^{-1}(x) \vee \varphi^{-1}(y)) \leq \max \{ f_A(\varphi^{-1}(x)), f_A(\varphi^{-1}(y)) \}$

$\varphi^{-1}(B)$ is vague join semi-lattice L_1 .

Hence the theorem follows.